

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NLFL) 2019

Board:

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During the annual CAA meeting in Krakow quite a lot of people from the CAA-NLFL chapter were present and contributed in various ways. For example the workshop *Improving presentation skills* was co-organized by one of our members. Various Sessions were (co-)organized by our members, such as:

- O29: Our little minions, part 2: small tools with major impact
- R09: Thinking out of the classroom: sharing knowledge and resources...
- R16: Where does global meet local? Finding common ground for multiscale analysis of settlement and land use dynamics
- S21: Challenges and opportunities of machine learning in archaeological research

In addition to sessions and workshops, various papers or contributions to sessions by our members can be found in the program of the CAA meeting in Krakow (https://2019.caaconference.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/25/2019/04/CAA2019_programabstracts_v20190423.pdf). The active role of various members in discussions is hard to track, but is often well visible during the conference. Many of the contributions by our members were often together with people from all over the globe, that our chapter plays an active role in the international community

We have organized a day of workshops in cooperation with the Digital Archaeology Group from Leiden University on 5th of April (<https://www.caanfl.nl/?q=node/68>). The DAWN (Digital Archaeology Workshops Netherlands-Flanders) was a success. In total around 70 people participated, about 2/3 academic (students and staff) and 1/3 from local governments or commercial companies. In the morning we organized two workshops (Programming in R and 3D modeling in Archaeology). In the afternoon we organized 2 workshops (GIS and Database Integration and Image Based Modeling in the Field). The workshops were sponsored by Amsterdam Centre for Ancient Studies and Archaeology (UvA), the 4D Research Lab and Archon (<http://www.archonline.nl/>). Following the success of the 2018 and 2019 workshops, we are organizing a similar day of workshops in 2020 (<http://digarchgroup.nl/dawn/>).

On the 28th and 29th of October, we held our annual Local Chapter Meeting (<http://www.caanfl.nl/?q=node/69>). The meeting took place in Leuven (Belgium) at the Faculty of Arts of the KU Leuven. The event was made up of a workshop-day (28th) and the actual meeting day with presentations (29th).

Topics for the hands-on workshops were:

- agent-based modelling in archaeology;
- spatial databases in archaeology;
- archaeological linked data and semantic web;
- archaeological spatial data visualisations using R.

In addition to 11 papers with varying topics in the field of computer applications in archaeology, it was with great pleasure that we could confirm keynote lectures by Prof. Dr. Mark Gillings (University of Leicester) and Prof. Dr. Gary Lock (University of Oxford), two leading scholars in the field of digital archaeology. In total, approximately 35 people (from both Flanders and the Netherlands, and with

academic and commercial backgrounds) participated at the workshop-day. At the meeting day, around 45 people were present. On the evening of the 29th, nearly everyone gathered in a nearby pub, resulting in meeting new and old friends an important goal of the CAA.